

Local Government in Argentina

Responses to Urban-Rural Challenges

edited by

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The H2020-MSCA-RISE-2018 project aims to provide solutions for local governments that address the fundamental challenges resulting from urbanisation. To address these complex issues, 18 partners from 17 countries and six continents share their expertise and knowledge in the realms of public law, political science, and public administration. LoGov identifies, evaluates, compares, and shares innovative practices that cope with the impact of changing urban-rural relations in major local government areas (WP 1-5).

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Local Financial Arrangements

3.1. Local Financial Arrangements in Argentina: An Introduction

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Addressing socioeconomic problems is mostly a subnational task in Argentina, as in many other decentralized countries. In the midst of adjustment reforms and deep economic crisis in the 1990s, the national government initiated a process of retrenchment and reduced significantly the social services it delivered. Associated to it, policy responsibilities of subnational units dramatically increased after the 1990s decentralization policies. Several key social services, such as primary health and education, are policy responsibilities of subnational units in Argentina (as well as in the most decentralized federal systems, such as Brazil and Mexico, and even in some decentralized unitary countries, such as Colombia). These decentralized social services are crucial to improve socioeconomic indicators at the subnational level.

Municipal governments in Argentina have 6 per cent of the total revenues and 9 per cent of the total spending. These shares are 16 and 33 for provinces and 80 and 58 for the federal government.⁴³ This imbalance means that subnational units have to rely on two main sources of revenue to face dire socioeconomic conditions: their own revenue (that is, the revenue they collect autonomously) and federal transfers they receive from the central government. Local governments collect very few taxes (such as garbage and lightning service fees), which represent about 40 per cent of municipal total revenue, and depend on provincial as well as federal transfers, which are about 50 per cent of their total revenue.⁴⁴ Some of them are automatic transfers (such as those from the revenue sharing system) and other discretionary. Without federal transfers, more disadvantaged provinces and municipalities depend on their own revenue to deliver vital social services. This severely diminishes their capacity to deal with the social problems they face, especially because their own revenue is lower than the national average and they usually have to deal with worse social indicators (and in most cases, they have poorly trained professionals with low salaries to deliver them).

References to Scientific and Non-Scientific Publications

López Acotto A and Maccioli M, 'La estructura de la recaudación municipal en la Argentina: alcances, limitaciones y desafíos' (Ministerio del Interior 2015)

⁴³ Alejandro López Acotto and Mariano Maccioli, 'La estructura de la recaudación municipal en la Argentina: alcances, limitaciones y desafíos' (Ministerio del Interior 2015) 24.

⁴⁴ *ibid* 26.

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